

Comparing AI Model Functionality for Data Visualization Using Baseline Metrics and Prompt Engineering

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Abstract—As the use of large language models (LLMs) expands into scientific workflows, their ability to generate high-quality biomedical data visualizations remains largely unvalidated. In this project, we evaluated the performance of three state-of-the-art AI models: ChatGPT-4o (OpenAI), Gemini 1.5 (Google), and DeepSeek R1 (DeepSeek) in creating visualizations from a biomedical dataset under two conditions: (1) open-ended prompting with minimal instruction, and (2) refined, structured prompting with explicit criteria for clarity, color accessibility, and interpretability. Each model was tasked with generating a series of plots to summarize clinical patterns within a labeled tumor dataset. We qualitatively assessed each output for design clarity, statistical relevance, visual accessibility, and conciseness. Initial prompts revealed substantial variation in plot quality and interpretive value. Through targeted prompt engineering, all models demonstrated improved outputs, with ChatGPT-4o excelling in statistical clarity, Gemini offering creative visualizations without guidance, and DeepSeek providing minimal yet clean figures while struggling to produce fully-working code solutions. Our findings suggest that prompt specificity, especially regarding accessibility, layout simplicity, and variable prioritization, significantly enhances figure quality across models. These insights underscore the importance of prompt design in leveraging AI tools for biomedical data visualization and present a roadmap for future standardization of AI-augmented figure generation.

Keywords—Language-learning models (LLMs), Biomedical Data Visualization, Prompt Engineering

I. BACKGROUND

Currently, biomedical research relies significantly on high-complexity and high-dimensional large data sets to recognize trends that are critical in the analysis of disease and can be used to further clinical decision-making [1]. For cancer, cell morphology is central to accurate diagnosis. Features such as cell radius, texture, and compactness are used to distinguish malignant tissue from benign tissue [2]. Therefore, the representation of these sets of data through graphs and plots is required for identifying patterns and correlations that aren't apparent when using raw data alone.

Traditionally, producing high-quality visualizations has required expertise in data analysis software and programming languages. This is a labor-intensive process

that is normally subjective depending on the analyst's requirements or limitations [3]. With advanced AI models, particularly large language models (LLMs), there is growing interest in utilizing AI to assist with interpreting data in the event of automated visualization.

Models such as OpenAI's ChatGPT-4o, Google's Gemini 2.5 Pro, and DeepSeek R1 now offer the ability to process natural language prompts and generate visual outputs directly from structured data. These tools promise to make visualization faster, more accessible, and potentially more insightful. However, differences in model architecture, training data, and reasoning capability mean that the quality and relevance of outputs can vary. Evaluating the performance of these models on biomedical data is essential when researchers begin including them in research pipelines. Analyzing these models cautiously will help build confidence in AI-derived results being accurate and reliable, a component that would be essential to inducing the broader use of AI tools in the context of biomedical research [4].

II. PURPOSE

This project aims to evaluate and compare the ability of three AI models, ChatGPT-4o, Gemini 2.5 Pro, and DeepSeek R1, to generate meaningful biomedical data visualizations from a cancer dataset. The dataset includes morphological features of tissue samples such as cell radius, texture, perimeter, area, smoothness, and compactness, recorded as both mean and worst values. These features are labeled according to diagnostic outcomes: benign or malignant.

The objectives of this study are twofold: (1) to assess how effectively each AI model can generate visually clear and biologically relevant graphs from the dataset when given complete freedom; and (2) to explore how prompt engineering influences output quality. This work adds to a deeper understanding of how AI tools can enhance biomedical research and the interpretability of complex data sets employed in cancer diagnosis. Moreover, through methodological comparison of the performance and limitations of each model, this study offers a foundation for building trust towards AI-facilitated workflows, a key step toward enabling reliable and facile adoption of AI in biomedical research environments.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study evaluates the effectiveness of three large language models (LLMs) in autonomously and semi-autonomously generating biomedical data visualizations using a shared dataset and a consistent prompting structure. The models tested were ChatGPT-4o (OpenAI), Gemini 2.5 Pro (Google), and DeepSeek R1 (DeepSeek), each accessed through their respective official web interfaces (chat.openai.com, Google AI Studio, and deepseek.com). No use of APIs, coding environments, or plugin-enhanced tools was employed to ensure that the models were evaluated within typical end-user conditions.

The dataset used for this study is titled Cancer_Data.csv, which contains numerical attributes extracted from cellular components of tumor samples. These attributes represent features of benign and malignant cell clusters, though no specific outcome or label column was used to guide the models initially. The dataset includes common clinical metrics such as cell size, uniformity, clump thickness, mitosis, and others, many of which are used in diagnostic contexts. To preserve the authenticity of a real-world user scenario, no preprocessing, filtering, or manual cleaning of the dataset was performed before uploading it into each model's interface. The visualization process was executed in two distinct phases: baseline prompting and refined prompt engineering.

In the first stage, each model was provided with an identical baseline prompt designed to encourage unconstrained creativity and insight discovery. The initial prompt read:

“I have attached here a CSV file of data for cancer data. Make and output here visualizations of data you feel is most relevant. That is your only constraint—you have freedom otherwise.”

This phase was used to assess the models' ability to autonomously identify key trends, select variables of interest, and design clear, clinically meaningful visualizations without further human instruction.

In the second stage, model-specific refined prompts were crafted based on each model's strengths, weaknesses, and previous output behavior. These prompts were more direct and incorporated known principles of effective data visualization, including plot type restrictions (2–3 plots maximum), clarity in layout, and adherence to color accessibility standards. Each model received a prompt tailored to its own generative characteristics:

- **ChatGPT-4o:**
“Create up to 3 visualizations that highlight the strongest clinical or statistical insights. Use colorblind-friendly palettes and avoid clutter. Prioritize clarity and plot titles.”

- **Gemini 2.5 Pro:**
“Visualize the 2–3 most important variable relationships in the dataset. Emphasize clean spacing, accessible colors, and clear, non-overlapping charts.”
- **DeepSeek R1:**
“Produce 2 clean, interpretable plots that clearly separate variables of interest. Use large labels, simple color schemes, and prioritize uncluttered space.”

The provided prompts were designed to foster the application of key principles emphasized throughout this course. These principles included the reduction of extraneous visual elements to enhance clarity, the simplification of comparative analyses to facilitate interpretation, and the strategic delegation of plot selection to the AI model. This delegation was intended to leverage the AI's capacity to identify and present visualizations that most effectively communicated statistically significant findings or clinically relevant insights within the dataset.

The outputs of each model were evaluated subjectively by the user based on four core criteria: (1) Visual Quality – including color use, font sizing, axis clarity, and spacing. (2) Readability & Layout – how easily the visualization could be interpreted at a glance. (3) Accessibility – adherence to colorblind-friendly palettes and overall legibility. (4) Clinical & Reader Relevance – whether the visualizations captured clinically meaningful trends or highlighted core relationships.

No automated or quantitative metrics were used for scoring. Instead, plots were compared side-by-side for intuitive interpretability and practical application in a biomedical research context.

Among the three models, ChatGPT-4o and Gemini 2.5 both successfully generated clean and executable Python/Matplotlib/Seaborn code for their visualizations. Both models required minimal intervention and were capable of explaining their plot choices with reasonable clinical intuition. In contrast, DeepSeek R1 struggled with code generation in multiple instances. Its initial heatmap code produced errors due to invalid methods and syntax, requiring manual correction by the user. DeepSeek was also the slowest to respond and required additional effort to make its plots usable, though its final images were visually simple and legible. All plots generated by the model are in the Appendix.

IV. RESULTS & CONCLUSIONS

In our initial observation, we compared the outcome of three models of AI—ChatGPT, Gemini, and DeepSeek—on one set of input data to identify how their performances differ when considering diagnostic patterns on tumor data. ChatGPT produced a chain of visualizations that represented each variable by its distribution, giving an accurate view into what individual data features are doing. This approach allowed for a careful examination of how various quantitative values varied between the datasets. Gemini and

DeepSeek, on the other hand, generated numbers that were concerned with the general distribution of benign and malignant tumors and provided a broader but less granular perspective. While each had a different emphasis, all three models could generate graphs examining single variables in terms of malignancy status. In addition, all the models produced a correlation matrix, which helped identify relationships between key variables. Interestingly, ChatGPT was observed to take a more analytical route, focusing on complex inter-variable relationships, while Gemini and DeepSeek were more inclined to produce figures specifically targeting diagnostic classifications.

To further optimize the outputs, we applied prompt engineering, modifying the input instructions given to each model to elicit diagnostic relevance. ChatGPT worked best with these updated prompts, generating visualizations that more clearly distinguished between malignant and benign cases. Its greater focus on clinical significance made its outputs particularly valuable for predictive analytics. DeepSeek, on the other hand, improved only slightly, generating again a few of the same figures of the initial run, suggesting a limitation in its capacity to react to prompt changes. Gemini showed average adaptability, gaining some benefit from the highly tuned prompts but still having a tendency towards structural output and code generation rather than thorough analysis. Overall, prompt engineering was a useful tool for aligning the analytical aspirations of the three models into concordance. Based on this comparative analysis, we concluded that ChatGPT was the strongest in output and visualization and, therefore, the most appropriate tool for exploratory data analysis in this case. Gemini was analytically weaker but came out stronger with code-related functionality. DeepSeek, as functional, gave the least impactful results against the rest of the models.

V. DISCUSSIONS

HOW EACH MODEL INITIALLY PERFORMED AT VISUALIZING TRENDS

In our study, we examined how three of the leading AI models, ChatGPT 4o, Gemini 2.5 Pro, and DeepSeek R1, performed at generating biomedical data visualizations in response to an open-ended initial prompt. In the absence of prompting, each model possessed individual strengths and weaknesses in trend identification, clinical relevance, and figure clarity.

ChatGPT 4o was able to initially show a strong ability to explore general quantitative trends across the dataset independently. It generated nice and technically sound plots that showed distributions of important features such as radius, texture, and area. The plots were well-organized and had correctly labeled axes. One major limitation, however, was that the direct outputs from ChatGPT sometimes did not have direct clinical interpretability, i.e., clearly separating malignant vs. benign cases (in this particular case with the cancer data set). Likewise, while the mathematical trends in the background were correctly captured, the biological relevance was not immediately pointed out.

Gemini 2.5 Pro approached the data differently. It quickly produced figures focused on simple diagnosis counts (malignant versus benign). This seemed to indicate a

faster recognition of the binary classification nature of the dataset. However, Gemini's initial outputs were more often than not overly simplistic. They lacked a deeper exploration of continuous variable relationships, such as how feature distributions differed between diagnosis groups, which limited their usefulness for more nuanced clinical insights. Overall, Gemini's early visualizations were appropriate but shallow.

DeepSeek R1 was the most inventive and creative baseline. It produced many scatterplots, pairwise correlations, and multi-variable explorations immediately. While this inventiveness was promising, it came at the cost of clarity. DeepSeek's outputs were congested, with duplicative plots, tight layouts, and poor organization. The figures did not highlight clinical questions and tended to render it more, instead of less, complicated to read trends relevant for diagnosis. DeepSeek needed more guidance to focus its outputs in a useful way.

Taken together, these initial impressions showed that while all three models could see trends and patterns in the data, ChatGPT approached consistent quantitative exploration in a superior manner, Gemini got easy clinical clusterings early, and DeepSeek showed latent potential buried under too much complexity (possibly the best to respond to prompting).

HOW PROMPT ENGINEERING IMPROVED THE MODELS:

Recognizing there might be a need for more diagnostic focus and clarity, we utilized prompt engineering, crafting prompts to expressly request the models to place comparisons between malignant and benign cases at the forefront, use clear labels, and select variables most predictive of clinical outcomes.

The overall Effects of Prompt Engineering were immediately noticeable. All three models excelled in the relevance and quality of their visualizations. Figures became more clinically meaningful to interpret, emphasizing diagnostic predictability. Visualizations also more readily separated malignant vs benign cohorts, an important factor in the analysis of medical data.

Post-prompting ChatGPT 4o became more concise in clinical narrative, connecting specific trends with diagnostic findings. Figures also had more effective use of color coding, clearer labeling, and greater biological relevance. ChatGPT produced consistently clean, reproducible figures that would be somewhat close to publication quality in scientific journals with further evaluation.

Gemini 2.5 Pro, after prompting, demonstrated tremendous relative improvement. It moved beyond basic diagnosis counts to more sophisticated visualizations like violin plots (showing distribution spread), correlation matrices, and diagnosis-specific scatterplots. Gemini's use of space, color accessibility, and plot depth significantly improved, although occasional issues like font sizing and minor layout crowding persisted.

DeepSeek R1 post-prompting saw the most significant improvement overall. The model reduced redundancy and produced elegant, ordered scatterplots that highlighted several meaningful relationships between features like concavity, radius, and texture, relationships that our team found ourselves. The plots were again close to publication quality and close to those of typical software used, adhering to biomedical convention and identifying diagnostic groupings. DeepSeek's improvement highlights the model's creative potential when properly guided.

Overall, prompt engineering was a necessary step for translating orbital AI outputs. This graduate formation transitioned into meaningful data visualizations, transforming raw figure generation into clinically applicable data, possibly informing action.

FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS & NEXT STEPS

Looking ahead, an immediate path forward is the inclusion of explicit figure guidelines within AI prompts themselves. In this project, we evaluated figures based on concepts learned in our class: utilization of space, legibility and labeling, color accessibility, and data appropriateness. Future workflows can include these specifications within prompts themselves, instructing models to:

- Maximize negative space utilization
- Enhance the salience of meaningful trends
- Ensure color palettes are colorblind-friendly.
- Label axes and titles clearly and concisely.

For example, a future prompt could read:

"Make a scatterplot of radius vs. perimeter, using a colorblind-friendly palette, with an emphasis on clear axis labeling and minimal extraneous chart elements."

By specifying these or any other standards explicitly, AI models could already generate higher-quality figures without requiring extensive human review. In addition, future research can explore the automation of evaluation metrics. Quantitative figure quality evaluation can be done without human judgment using computer vision or scoring rubrics.

Further, another interesting direction would be model strength integration, taking the structural form of ChatGPT and DeepSeek's creativity for hybrid figure generation pipelines. Finally, biomedical visualization models would be assisted by domain-specific fine-tuning. AIs trained on biomedical journals and visual best practices would further tune their output to clinical research requirements.

BROADER IMPLICATIONS

As AI is increasingly being integrated into biomedical research workflows, prompt engineering is a new form of science communication. Rather than merely generating

numbers, researchers must now collaborate with AI models, defining goals, adding constraints, and critically evaluating outputs.

While AI holds great promise for accelerating data visualization and analysis, human oversight remains paramount. The future of biomedical research will involve increasingly more humans defining clinical priorities and AI conducting visualizations and analysis, a synergy with the potential to make research faster, more reproducible, and more accessible across disciplines. All in all, this project demonstrates that although AI can generate biomedical images, it requires human-driven prompt engineering to turn the images from technically accurate to clinically meaningful.

VI. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION & ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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VII. APPENDIX

A. INITIAL PROMPT IMAGES

ChatGPT

DeepSeek

Gemini

Distribution of Cancer Diagnosis (M vs B)

B. ENGINEERED PROMPTS

ChatGPT

Gemini

Tumor Texture Distribution by Diagnosis

Tumor Size vs. Concave Points by Diagnosis

Tumor Radius Distribution by Diagnosis

DeepSeek

